

Boundary Spanners in Academia: The Economic Influence and Field Preferences

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Abstract

In academia, the role of the "boundary spanner"—which describes individuals or organizations capable of facilitating inter-organizational communication—is increasingly considered crucial for promoting knowledge communication and collaboration. This study defines a "boundary spanner" as a researcher who affiliates with organizations across sectoral boundaries and utilizes a bibliometric approach to explore the correlation between boundary spanners and economic growth, and the research field preference profile of these roles at the income group level. Tracking the development of boundary spanners' production and the strong association with GDP suggests the positive influence of economic growth. Our results regarding research field preference show that boundary spanners from high-income countries are active widely in most research fields, while in the upper-middle-income group, boundary spanners show a preference for fields related to mathematics, computer science, physical sciences, and engineering. Our findings, linking boundary spanners to economic growth, might offer fresh insights into the evolution of boundary spanners in academia.

1. Introduction

To tackle the complexity of contemporary societal issues, such as climate change and biodiversity loss, effective communication and collaboration among stakeholders from diverse sectors, including researchers, policymakers, and practitioners, is imperative (European Science Foundation, 2013). The concept of "boundary spanners"—individuals or processes that facilitate communication across different domains—first emerged in the organizational management field in the 1950s (March & Simon, 1958; Tushman, 1977). Initially, the term described practices aimed at knowledge exchange and operational effectiveness between organizations. Since then, its scope has broadened to include people and processes that transcend organizational boundaries.

The role of boundary spanners is critical, as they facilitate knowledge exchange and collaboration. Although there is a growing recognition of the benefits provided by boundary spanners, such as knowledge brokers, much of the evidence supporting their efficacy remains anecdotal (Cvitanovic et al., 2017). Today, bibliometric data offer a resource that can reveal patterns and trends in scientific activities. By analyzing bibliometric data, particularly author-organization affiliation links within publication records, we can trace the activity of boundary spanners in academia.

The objective of this paper is to move from anecdotal evidence to quantitative analysis by harnessing bibliometric data to examine the activities of academic boundary spanners on a large

scale. Specifically, researchers affiliated with multiple organizations are seen as indicative of boundary-spanning activities. These individuals are not only embedded in various affiliations but also serve as connectors that foster communication between organizations, culminating in scientific outputs such as publications. These outputs provide a unique lens through which boundary spanners can be observed.

Accordingly, our study aims to characterize and structure the role of boundary spanners in academia. Building upon previous work (Hottenrott & Lawson, 2017; Huang & Chang, 2018; Sanfilippo, Hewitt, & Mackey, 2018; Hottenrott, Rose, & Lawson, 2021; Yegros-Yegros, Capponi, & Frenken, 2021), we intend to explore the potential association between boundary spanners' production and economic growth, and map out the disciplinary landscape of boundary spanners' preferences by income-group level. The scope of this exploratory study is framed by the following research questions:

- (1) Is the growth of boundary spanners associated with economic growth?
- (2) Does the economic level influence boundary spanners' research field preference?

2. Data and Methods

2.1. Publication data collection

We retrieved publications from the Web of Science (WoS) Core Collection (SCI, SSCI) published between 2013 and 2022. Only publications of the Web of Science document types "Article" and "Review" were included in the data collection. Author-affiliation links contained within the publication records were used to trace authors' affiliations. This study analyzes more than 18 million publications and over 0.1 billion author-affiliation links.

2.2 Affiliation classification and author classification

Based on the Incites organization types and corresponding descriptions, we classified organizations into five types: academic sector, healthcare sector, government sector, corporate sector, and non-profit sector. Manual and AI-assisted institutional disambiguation and classification were undertaken. Moreover, we proposed a classification to define boundary-spanning authorship (here abbreviated as boundary spanners) within their publication records:

- Boundary spanners: authors with cross-sector multiple affiliations, e.g., an author has multiple affiliations; these affiliations are from more than one sector based on the organization types.

2.3. Countries' GDP and income group of classification

We used GDP data¹ and income group classification² from the World Bank, classifying each country into its income group for the newest fiscal year.

2.4 Disciplinary classification

The Incites citation topic is a research topic classification system with three levels-macro, meso, and micro level. It assigns each publication to one topic at each level. We utilized the meso-level topics (with 326 topics) to examine the boundary-spanning activity profile through the lens of a science map.

¹ <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.MKTP.CD>

² <https://datahelpdesk.worldbank.org/knowledgebase/articles/906519-world-bank-country-and-lending-groups>

2.5. Preference indicator: Activity index

Frame (1977) introduced the activity index to characterize the relative research effort a country devotes to a given research field. It's also similar to revealed competitive advantage (RCA) index proposed by Balassa (1965). With respect to a research field, the activity index (AI) of a country during the given period can be defined as:

$$AI_{c,f} = \frac{P_{c,f} / \sum_{i=1}^n P_{c,f}}{P_{w,f} / \sum_{i=1}^n P_{w,f}}$$

Where $P_{c,f}$ is the publications of country c in field f , $\sum_{i=0}^n P_{c,f}$ is the total publications of country c from all fields, $P_{w,f}$ is the publications of the world in field f , $\sum_{i=0}^n P_{w,f}$ is the total publications of country the world from all fields.

Since here this study look at the output led by boundary spanners (BS), we can define AI index correspondingly:

$$AI_{c,f,BS} = \frac{P_{c,f,BS} / \sum_{i=1}^n P_{c,f,BS}}{P_{w,f,BS} / \sum_{i=1}^n P_{w,f,BS}}$$

3. Results

3.1. Increasing boundary spanners' output and its association with economic growth

Publications authored by boundary spanners have shown an increase from 2013 to 2022, as depicted in Figure 1. About 50,000 scientific outputs were authored by boundary spanners in 2013, with the number growing to more than 90,000 by 2022.

Figure 1: Growth of global publications with boundary spanners.

Is there a positive association between the spanning activities of boundary spanners and economic growth? Evidence suggests that this may indeed be the case. Figure 2 presents a linear regression model with GDP as the independent variable and the volume of publications involving boundary spanners as the dependent variable. The translucent band outlines the 95% confidence interval, with each point representing a country.

Figure 2: Association between countries' GDP and number of publications with boundary spanners.

Our analysis reveals a strong positive correlation between the base-10 logarithm of the publication volumes of boundary spanners and the base-10 logarithm of GDP at the country level (Pearson correlation $r = 0.73$). Furthermore, the regression analysis indicates that an increase in GDP is associated with a greater number of boundary spanners' publications (1.3 times). However, while a correlation between the number of boundary spanners' publications and GDP exists, more sophisticated regressions and robustness checks are warranted.

Motivated by the link between the publication volumes of boundary spanners and economic growth, we explore the proportion of boundary spanner publications within the total scientific output by different economic levels, for instance, by income group.

Figure 3: Share of publications with boundary spanners by income group.

It should be noted that our analysis only includes the results from countries with relatively large scientific outputs over the past 10 years. As illustrated in Figure 3, the share of boundary spanners' publications varies when considering different countries' income groups. In the high-income group, the median value is approximately 16%, while the other three groups display relatively lower medians of boundary spanners' publication share: 7% in both upper-middle and lower-middle, and 5% in the low-income group.

3.2. *Disciplinary profile of boundary spanners' research preference by income group*

To explore the research field preferences of different income country groups, we employed a scientific knowledge graph visualization (Zhang & Shen, 2024), based on the InCites citation topic classification system. This approach revealed five clusters: Biomedical and Health Sciences, Life and Earth Sciences, Mathematics and Computer Science, Physical Sciences and Engineering, Social Sciences and Humanities—aligned with the CWTS's five main fields of science. For an in-depth explanation of the CWTS paper-level classification system's construction, we refer to two studies (Waltman & Van Eck, 2012; Traag, Waltman, & Van Eck, 2019) for a comprehensive introduction to the classification methods used to explore the relatedness of publications and their clustering into groups.

Using this graph visualization, we calculated the activity index for the publications of boundary spanners across 326 research topics, divided by four income groups. Figure 3 offers an overview of the research field preference behaviors of boundary spanners from different income groups.

Figure 4: Boundary spanners' field preference profile by income group.

In Figure 4, countries are categorized into four groups by their income level, arranged from left to right as follows: low, lower-middle, upper-middle, and high-income groups. In each profile graph, each dot represents a research topic, positioned to align with its overarching cluster. The color of the dots indicates the value of the activity index.

The result presented in Figure 4 clearly depicts the research preference landscapes of each income group's boundary spanners. Low-income and lower-middle-income countries demonstrate a lower level of activity in boundary spanners' outputs. The upper-middle-income group primarily engages in research within the Mathematics and Computer Science cluster, as well as the Physical Sciences and Engineering cluster. Conversely, high-income countries tend to be active across all five clusters, indicating a relatively wide research output activity.

4. Discussion

It is increasingly discussed that the role of boundary spanners is crucial for knowledge communication and collaboration in academia. However, the evidence-based exploration of global boundary spanners remains a question. Through the analysis of over 18 million scientific publications between 2013 and 2022, our large-scale study sheds light on the positive association between the scientific progress of temporal boundary spanners and economic growth. Additionally, we employed knowledge graph visualization and an activity index to reflect the research field preference of countries grouped by income level and provided a clue that economic factors would influence boundary spanners' field preference, with countries from the high-income group maintaining a broader research profile while the upper-income group exhibits a preference for more specialized fields.

This study faces several limitations. Primarily, it depends on a bibliographic database, potentially underestimating non-English-language research outputs. The association between economics and boundary spanners needs further causality investigation. Moreover, based on the current results by income group level, we need a further in-depth analysis at the country level.

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Author contributions

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Competing interests

Authors have no competing interests.

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